

TESSERA

NEWSLETTER

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ISSUE 1

TESSERA IN A NUTSHELL

The TESSERA project welcomes you in it's 1st Newsletter!

Seven organisations from three different countries joined forces in TESSERA, a new **Internal Security Fund EU project**, which aims to conduct the preparatory work needed to identify the **conditions and requirements** for the creation of **high-quality large-scale trusted and shareable datasets** supporting the **European Security Data Space for Innovation**. The project also aims to specify the **low-level architecture of the data-related national components of the European Security Data Space**, foster the involvement of stakeholders, organise technical workshops, and produce a report documenting its outcomes.

● Project Details

GA Number: 101145802
Start Date: March 2024
Duration: 24 months
Call: ISF-2022-TF1-AG-DATA
Project coordinator: CERTH

● Consortium

The TESSERA consortium team consists of **seven** partners, including **Law Enforcement Agencies, Research Institutions, and Industry Experts in Security and AI**, as well as **Legal and Ethical Specialists** from three EU countries.

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News & Events

TESSERA at the RISE-SD 2024 Conference

The TESSERA project, represented by its coordinator, the **M4D group at Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)**, was honoured to participate as a co-organizing project at the two-day **RISE-SD 2024 event** in Chalkidiki, Greece.

The event convened European research and development communities in Civil Security to highlight the achievements of European Security Research, promote debate, and showcase the results of European R&D security projects.

[Read More on our website!](#)

TESSERA Kick-off Meeting

The project kicked-off in March 2024 in a two-day meeting (06-07 Mar.) at the premises of CERTH in Thessaloniki, Greece, covering a comprehensive agenda and coming to a clear action plan for the upcoming months.

[Read More on our website!](#)

WHAT'S NEXT?

The TESSERA consortium wishes you a prosperous New Year!

Exciting milestones await the TESSERA project in 2025, promising a year of impactful progress and innovation!

Stay tuned with the TESSERA project.

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